

Exploring the Factors Affecting Learning Motivation of LNU Social Studies Major Amidst Online Learning Experience

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Abstract:- The objectives of this study are to identify the factors that affect the learning motivation of the LNU social studies students amidst an online learning environment and find out how it affects their learning motivation as well as their personal coping mechanisms to address such an issue. To carry out this study successfully, the researchers used a hermeneutic phenomenological research design, a qualitative research method that focuses on the participants' personal experiences with a specific phenomenon. This study is composed of fourteen (14) identified samples from the BSED social studies students of Leyte Normal University. They were chosen through a non-probability sampling technique called the purposive sampling technique. In the data collection process, the researchers ensure ethical consideration and observe the components of trustworthiness, which include credibility, transferability, dependability, and conformability, to ensure the validity of the data. According to the narratives and thematic analysis, the study revealed and identified factors including internal factors, health-related factors, lack of social interaction, non-conducive learning set-up, family issues/instability, lack of resources, and teachers' behavior and personality as the major factors that affect the learning motivation of the BSED social studies students at LNU, all of which influenced the motivation of students in so many ways. This includes being unproductive, inefficient, distracted, and worst of all, demotivated. In response, among their personal coping mechanisms are establishing peer support systems, effective time management, taking enough rest and perseverance.

Keywords:- learning motivation; internal factors, health-related factors, lack of social interaction, non-conducive learning set-up, family issues/instability, lack of resources, teachers' behavior and personality, unproductive, inefficient, distracted, demotivated, peer support systems, effective time management, taking enough rest and perseverance.

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Background of the Study

Globally, the COVID-19 pandemic has had a significant negative influence on students' abilities to learn. Students and teachers have been forced to shift from traditional classrooms to emergency online or remote learning. The transition of their methods from a focus on face-to-face learning to an online learning environment mediated by various forms of technology presents significant problems. The pandemic reveals the urgent need to augment the educational system's technological infrastructure, expand the teachers' pedagogical expertise, and enrich the students' learning repertoire (Chiu & Lin, 2021). The online learning regulation is in force for all educational institutions. It has transferred knowledge from traditional face-to-face approaches to remote digital platforms. This sudden transformation has been debatable due to the quality of education it has resulted in. Some previous studies revealed that online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic has caused advantages, while others have caused disadvantages (Firman & Rahayu, 2020).

The capacity of students to engage in meaningful multimodal communication, assume agency in their learning, and build conceptual and epistemic understanding through active use of digital resources are all crucial components of online learning (Hartnett, 2016). In such online contexts, the critical roles of students' self-regulation, motivation, and positive learning dispositions are accentuated (Chiu & Hew, 2018). Although these pertinent issues have been covered in a sizable number of studies in the area of educational technology, there is still a dearth of research on how to effectively adapt relevant learning and motivational theories to create efficient and long-lasting online pedagogy in complex, multifaceted, and even situational online learning environments.

Online learning has caused a lack of motivation for some students to learn, whereas others are highly motivated (Cahyani, Listiana, & Larasati, 2020). As the online teaching and learning processes used computer technology, it increased the enthusiasm of both teachers and students to participate, which, in turn, increased their computer skills too (Dasrun et al. 2020). On the other hand, online learning was also described as bringing disadvantages. The students claimed that online learning had caused them psychological problems and some health problems like fatigue, headaches, or fever because they had too many assignments to do in a short time. Some also declared that they had impaired

eyesight due to long-term staring at computers or phone screens. Students also faced hardship in financial terms because they had to buy large amounts of credit for online quotas (Simamora, 2020). However, during the pandemic, the advantages and disadvantages that determined students' learning success were closely related to students' motivation in online learning.

On April 28, 2020, the entire city of Tacloban was placed under General Community Quarantine (GCQ). It became effective when Tacloban's local government issued Executive Order 2020-04-020 that ordered the city-wide implementation of General Community Quarantine starting May 1 to May 15, unless otherwise extended. The said implementation has had a huge impact on every aspect of society, including the economy, transportation, mobility, and even education. The education sector had been much affected by this pandemic and had faced several struggles in continuing education despite various restrictions being imposed. All the public and private schools, universities, and state colleges around the city have been forced to close their operations to conduct face-to-face regular classes. Leyte Normal University (LNU) president Jude Duarte announced that the university will start using online platforms such as Moodle and any other available means to reach the students. In his speech during the kickoff of the student on-boarding program, he addresses that "the very first question that will come up in your mind is: Will it be online-pure online? Will it be hybrid-or a combination of face to-face My answer to that is, "For now, we will start using an online platform." This is in adherence to the CHED COVID Advisory No. 7 issued on May 04, 2020, which paves the way for the suspension of the conduct of face-to-face or in-person classes until further directives from the IATF or issuance by the proper government authority that the province or city will be under MGCQ.

The purpose of this study is to improve our learning performance, enhance our wellbeing, personal growth, or sense of purpose and change our ways of thinking, feeling, and behaving. Under Memorandum 4 series of 2020, the CHED gave schools and universities more leeway to design and deliver innovative learning programs and interventions. Thus, this study will help the students find ways to increase motivation in crucial situations in order to change behavior, develop competencies, be creative, set goals, grow interests, make plans, develop talents, and boost engagement. Because when our motivation is depleted, our functioning and wellbeing suffer. Some studies show that when we feel helpless in exerting control, for example, we tend to give up quickly when challenged (Peterson, Maier, & Seligman, 2019). Others have proven that when we find ourselves coerced, we lose access to our inner motivational resources (Ryan & Deci 2017). Thus, high-quality motivation allows us to thrive, while its deficit causes us to flounder. Greater student engagement, improved employee job satisfaction, flourishing relationships, and successful institutions are all examples of how higher motivation helps society.

B. Statement of the Problem

This research aims to explore and identify the factors affecting the learning motivation of Social Studies majors in LNU amidst an online learning experience. It also seeks to answer the following questions:

- What are the factors that affects the learning Motivation of the Social Studies Students amidst the online learning experience?
- How does the factors affects the learning Motivation of the Social Studies students?
- What are the coping mechanisms or personal remedies of the students in dealing with the Factors that affects their learning Motivation?

C. Theoretical Framework

The study is anchored from the theoretical support of McClelland's Achievement Motivation Theory and Maslow's Theory of Motivation the Hierarchy of Needs. The concept behind the framework shows the connection between two theories that will support the two factors which are the intrinsic and extrinsic Motivation factors that has been often used to explore students' reasons for engagement in online environment (e.g., Mortens, Gulikers, & Bastiaens, 2004; Xie et al., 2006). The extrinsic Influences and factors; impact student learning Motivation through, external rewards just like grading systems, employee evaluations, awards and accolades, and the respect and admiration of others., factors and some extrinsic Motivation that affects the learning of students. Intrinsic Motivation are unique to each other learning Motivation and are rooted in individual personality. Intrinsic Motivation incorporates a variety of concepts like our core values, our interests, and our personal sense of morality. These factors may be possible to change as the student learning Motivation.

McClelland started his work in the 1940s and it gave rise to the Achievement Motivation Theory. In the Methods of Measuring Human Motivation chapter of Atkinson's book *Reasons in Fantasy, Action, and Society* from 1958, McClelland provided an explanation of human motives. At that moment, McClelland recognized the affiliation motive, the power motive, the sexual motive, and the achievement motive as human motives. However, McClelland narrowed his focus on the needs for Achievement, Affiliation, and Power in his later book *The Achieving Society* (McClelland, 1961).The main tenet of McClelland's theory is that people are driven in varied degrees by their wants for achievement, power, and affiliation, and that these requirements are taught or acquired throughout the course of a person's lifetime (Daft, 2008; Lussier & Achua, 2007). In other words, most people have a combination of the three needs and will show it.

Need for Achievement. The requirement for Achievement was described by McClelland, Atkinson, Clark, and Lowell (1958) as "success in competition with some criterion of perfection. In other words, a character in the novel wants to succeed in a competition while maintaining a certain level of brilliance. Even if the person doesn't succeed in achieving this objective, the worry about competing against a high standard of perfection allows one to recognize the desired goal as an achievement goal. So, this is how we

would define an achievement generally (p. 181). According to McClelland et al. (1958), competition with a standard of excellence was most obvious when a person was in direct competition with another person, but it may also be shown in the concern for how well one person completes a work, independent of how well another person is performing. "The need for achievement is the unconscious concern for perfection in accomplishments through individual efforts," claim Lussier and Achua (2007). (p. 42). The need for Achievement, according to Daft (2008), is "the drive to accomplish something tough, attain a high standard of success, master complex tasks, and surpass others" (p. 233). Individuals who exhibit the need for Achievement seek to accomplish realistic but challenging goals (Moore & Rotter, 2010).

Need for Power. The need for power, according to McClelland (1961), is "a concern 'with the control of the means of influencing a person'" (p. 167). The thirst for power, according to Lussier and Achua (2007), is "the unconscious concern for influencing others and pursuing positions of authority" (p. 42). The drive to influence or control others, to be accountable for others, and to exercise authority over others is how Daft (2008) characterized the urge for power (p. 233). Individuals who exhibit the need for Power have a desire to be influential and want to make an impact (Moore & Rotter, 2010).

Need for Affiliation. When defining the need for Affiliation, McClelland (1961) stated, "Affiliation...establishing, maintaining, or restoring a positive affective relationship with another person. The word "friendship" sums up our relationship the best (p. 160). Because of this, "the urge for affiliation is the unconscious concern for establishing, preserving, and reestablishing close human relationships" (Lussier & Achua, 2007, p. 43). "The drive to build intimate personal ties, avoid conflict, and establish warm friendships" is how Daft (2008) characterized the need for affiliation (p. 233). People who display a craving for affiliation are drawn to social interactions (Moore & Rotter, 2010).

American psychologist Abraham Maslow proposed a hierarchy of psychological requirements to explain human decision-making in a 1943 study titled "A Theory of Human Motivation." Maslow claimed that five essential needs constitute the basis for human behavioral motivation in his first work and subsequent 1954 book, *Motivation and Personality*. Maslow argues that an individual's behavior is dictated by five categories of human needs. Some of these needs include those for physical well-being, safety, love and belonging, esteem, and self-actualization.

Basic needs are at the bottom of a pyramid-shaped hierarchy of requirements according to Maslow's theory, with higher-level, intangible need at the top. When a person's basic needs are met, he or she can move on to higher-level needs.

Physiological needs: Physiological needs are the first of Maslow's hierarchy's id-driven lower wants. Food and water, adequate rest, clothing and shelter, overall health, and reproduction are among the most fundamental human

survival needs. According to Maslow, basic physiological requirements must be met before humans may progress to the next stage of fulfillment.

Safety needs: Are next on the list of lower-level requirements. Aspects of safety that are crucial include defense against assault and theft, mental stability and well-being, health security, and financial security.

Love and Belongingness needs: On the third level of Maslow's hierarchy, social needs are the last of the so-called lower requirements and have to do with interpersonal relationships. Among these needs are friendships and family ties, both biological and chosen (parents, siblings, and children) (spouses and partners). Physical and emotional intimacy, ranging from sexual engagements to profound emotional attachments, are required to establish a sense of greater kinship. This urge is also satisfied by belonging to social groupings, such as a union, club, or team of coworkers, or by developing an identity within one.

Esteem needs: The higher demands are ego-driven ones, starting with esteem. The two most crucial elements of esteem are self-respect and self-esteem (the belief that you are valuable and deserving of respect) (confidence in your potential for personal growth and accomplishments). According to Maslow, there are two different types of self-esteem: esteem based on other people's respect and appreciation, and esteem based on your own self-evaluation. Self-assurance and independence are fostered by this type of self-esteem.

Self-Actualization needs: Realizing your full human potential is referred to as "self-actualization." Maslow's hierarchy of needs places self-actualization needs, often referred to as self-fulfillment wants, at its summit. Education, skill development—the honing of abilities in fields like music, athletics, design, cuisine, and gardening—caring for others, and bigger ambitions like learning a new language, traveling to new places, and receiving awards are a few instances of self-actualization criteria.

To sum up, the intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, comes together and affects the learning motivation of the students. This will help them distinguished the factors that affects their learning Motivation and keeps them motivated in learning amidst online learning experience.

D. Scope and Delimitation

This study covers the factors that affects the learning motivation of the BSED social studies students of Leyte Normal University. The entire study is conducted using a qualitative research design wherein the experiences of the students in certain phenomena will be collected and analyzed. The study is delimited only to the fourteen identified students who are currently studying via online learning set-up at Leyte Normal University particularly located in Tacloban City. All the identified participants are students under Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in Social Studies for the School Year 2021-2022. One of the weaknesses of this study is the insufficient number of participants that would compose our sample. But since this study focuses on the personal experiences of the students about their motivation in an

online learning set-up, all the identified participants are assumed to share related experiences and therefore data saturation will be highly observed. Furthermore, the credibility and reliability of the data collected from the participants are highly prioritized and ensured.

E. Significance of the Study

This study is designed to identify and describe the Factors affecting learning motivation among Social Studies major in LNU amidst Online learning experience. On the other hand, this study will be beneficial to the following:

- a) **LEYTE NORMAL UNIVERSITY**
This study would help the university to achieve its set standards and educational goal towards its students. It will help them as well in the realization of the university's II and vision as well as its core values despite of the challenges that everybody is facing at this present time.
- b) **SCHOOL ADMINISTRATION**
This research study would help the school administrator in formulating remedies that would help the students to enhance their learning motivation through incorporating some engaging activities and implementing certain school regulations in the modular learning that is being implemented in the university.
- c) **FACULTY AND STAFF**
To the faculty of Leyte Normal University specially in the social studies unit, since they are also part of the students' academic progress, they can gain benefit from this research study as they will be guided and be informed with the current situation of the students and their struggles in a remote learning modality. It will serve as their benchmark in creating for an initiative in enhancing the learning motivation of the students and translating the learning process in a digitalized world memorable and productive.
- d) **PARENTS**
The Parents, as the first person responsible in the entire learning process of the students can gain some insights in this study that would be beneficial in helping their son/daughter to boost their motivation to learn despite of the challenges that this pandemic is bringing to us. This could be done by any other means depending on the recommendation of this study.
- e) **STUDENTS**
This study will also offer great significance to the students because it will help them to awaken their awareness on the factors affecting their learning Motivation amidst online learning. Thus, allowing them to establish plans and personal coping strategies in dealing with this problem.
- f) **FUTURE RESEARCHERS**
To the future researchers who will spend time venturing the same problems or issues, this research study will serve as their paradigm and a comprehensive related literature for their study.

F. Definition of Terms

To provide better understanding on this research, the technical terms are hereby operationally defined:

Covid-19. A coronavirus-caused acute respiratory infection in humans that can cause severe symptoms and, in some cases, death, especially in the elderly and those with underlying medical issues.

Pandemic. A disease that affects numerous countries or continents.

Face to Face. Face to face refers to learning set up, where student and teacher has physical encounter.

Learning Motivation. Learning motivation refers to the students' persistence to learn amidst online learning.

Blended learning. Students learn through electronic and online media as well as traditional face-to-face instruction in this type of education.

Online learning experience. Online learning experience is defined as the different aspects of learning and teaching process experienced by the students.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

This Chapter presents the relevant literature and studies that the Researchers considered in strengthening the importance of the present study. It also presents synthesis of the art to fully understand the research for better comprehension of the study.

A. Factor's that affects Learning Motivation

Motivation is an internal construct that guides, changes, or maintains objectives, activities, and preferences, according to Bzuneck (2001). It is also often known as the "engine of learning" (Paris & Turner, 1994), influences what, how, and when students learn (Schunk & Usher, 2012). Ryan and Deci (2000a, 2000b) suggested that motivated learners are capable of engaging in demanding learning activities that engage them actively in discovering appropriate techniques to support their learning, enjoy them, and demonstrate competence, persistence, and creative learning in their studies. Furthermore, Koff & Mullis (2011), emphasizes that learning motivation is the student's intention or desire to participate in and make efforts in learning, as measured by the student's choice of specific learning activities and their efforts in those activities. In this study, learning motivation is defined as an engine that leads students' continuing learning and efforts toward the learning goal specified by teachers during the learning process. Additionally, students' intrinsic interests and teachers' or parents' extrinsic rewards could be combined to produce learning motivation in the classroom. Intrinsic and extrinsic motivation are the two sorts of motivation in this case. When we behave without any visible external incentives, this is known as intrinsic motivation. We simply enjoy an activity or see it as a chance to learn, grow, and realize our full potential." (2010, Coon & Mitterer). "Extrinsic motivation, on the other hand, refers to our proclivity to engage in activities for recognized external rewards, whether they are material (e.g., money) or

psychological (e.g., praise) in nature.” (Psychology of Motivation, Brown, 2007). Deci and Ryan (2000) postulated a continuum of internalization of behavioral rules that progresses via several types of extrinsic incentive until they reach the motivational level that is more self-regulated and autonomous, intrinsic motivation (Deci & Vansteenkiste, 2004). ‘Intrinsic motivation is defined as the practicing of an activity for its inherent satisfactions rather than for some separate consequence,’ according to Ryan and Deci (2000a, p.56). Internal factors such as interest, enjoyment, or challenge that an individual acquires in completing activities are linked to the joy or satisfaction that is integrated in the activities. They also described extrinsic motivation as “a construct that applies whenever an activity is performed in order to achieve some distinct consequence” (Ryan & Deci, 2000a, p.60). It has to deal with external influences in undertaking things, such as receiving a reward or acknowledgment from others (Hartnett, 2016). In this study, intrinsic and extrinsic motivation are employed as measure dimensions of learning motivation, according to the above research.

Moreover, a study conducted by Avila et. al (2021) claims that there are varieties of factors that influence students’ academic success during online learning, including teaching methods, psychological factors, proficiency level, and language skills, which can motivate them to develop learning strategies based on their exposure to certain educational technologies that students and teachers use. The study also showed that the students perceived that distance learning amidst pandemic is good and necessary, however, the accessibility of devices that is necessary for on-line learning is sometimes not available and averagely available. In addition, the students perceived that sometimes the University and the teachers are moderately helpful in offering resources (Avila et. al 2021). In addition, the study of Avila et. al (2021) also revealed that the students are being overwhelmed in this type of learning environment because it is unfamiliar to them.

Furthermore, a study conducted by Harnet, (2016) cited in Gustiani S. (2020), the absence of both intrinsic and extrinsic motivations in every student is referred to as amotivation. It occurs when students feel the unwillingness and low driving force in learning, self-degradation and low self- efficacy. They believe that learning outcomes are irrelevant as it doesn’t satisfy their expectations and has less value in returns. Similarly, Sison et. al (2021) students’ have a high self-efficacy amidst Covid-19 pandemic. Despite various factors that may affect self-efficacy and motivation, Sison et. al (2021), predicts a higher academic success in all fields of expertise among students. In addition, Sison et. al (2021) claims that, “Motivation and self-efficacy influence each other, and having such good self-efficacy can motivate the students to do well in school and increase their academic success”.

B. Online learning

The concept of online learning had already been elaborated and interpreted by several scholars. According to Bate, (2005) online learning is a method of teaching done or mediated by web and internet. On the other hand, Ally (2008, p.5) defines online learning as a form of teaching with the use of internet to access learning materials, interact with the teachers and classmates as a way of obtaining support to learn effectively and to develop based on the learning experiences. Harnett (2016) in her book argued the definition of online learning as a combination of the two ideas. She defined it as: “...a distance education mediated by web and technology where students and teachers are geographically separated.”

C. Online learning during the pandemic.

The Covid 19 pandemic had really brought great devastation in each country and had impacted not just its economic, psychological and social aspects but also the education system at large Rotas E & Cahapay M. (2020). This global health crisis caused by the deadly corona virus had compelled every school and universities to declare temporary closure in compliance with the safety measures and health protocols implemented by the government. But with the government’s strong desire to continue the learning even despite of the closure, this paves way for the migration from the traditional classroom set up to an online and digitalized platforms of learning Gustiani S, (2020). According to the recent study of Li and Lalani (2020), it was found out that there is a total of 12.2 billion of student studying out from the classroom. This temporary reform in the education system has been debatable on its efficacy and outcomes. However, previous studies had found out and presented some advantages and disadvantages of online learning as an alternative to the traditional teaching approach. According to Firman and Rahayu (2020); Hidayat and Noeraida (2020); Simamora (2020), online learning is beneficial to the students in such ways that it gives them a strong interaction to various engaging learning materials despite of time and place differences. It offers great experiences for them to explore varied digital programs. Since online learning modality is mediated through technologies, both students and teachers would find it more engaging to teach and learn in this set up while improving their computer skills eventually Dasrun (2020); Khasanah, Pramudibyanite & Widuroyeki (2020).

On the other hand, online learning is also viewed in its disadvantages specially on the learner’s physical and psychological wellbeing. First, according to Gustiani S. (2020) online learning poses threat and risk on students’ health as they would spend more time facing on their computer screens which could emit harmful radiation that could directly damage their visions. Moreover, some students also complain that they were prone to experience health related problems like headache, fatigue, or fever because of lack of enough rest in the middle of compiled activities to be accomplished in just a short period of time (Simamora, 2020).

Online learning has also a great impact to the psychological and mental well-being of the students. This is

basically due to some circumstances that are far beyond one's control such as poor internet connectivity and financial problems that has direct impact on the students' performance and quarterly remarks. Online learning is a very challenging and demanding approach of learning. Others who are vulnerable are even prone to experience depression (Simamora, 2020).

Furthermore, a study conducted by Giray et. al (2021) revealed that students feel limited and exhausted from the existing educational set up amidst Covid-19 pandemic. Students even perceived that the quality of education was reduced because of studying by themselves which they deemed to be ineffective without the guidance of their teachers most of the time. This results to students having difficulty to comprehend their lessons. In addition, the study revealed that the reason of the student's motivation was due to external factors such as, the fear being left behind and not able to graduate at the same time with their batch mates. The students reasoned out that if they would not enroll and graduate the same time with their batch mates, they would commit a wrong choice and end up missing some opportunities. Furthermore, the study revealed that the students emphasize about graduating as soon as possible because they don't want to prolong their years in the University and to get a degree because it is a prerequisite in order to secure a stable job after college which showed an intrinsic motivation to continue studying (Giray et. al 2021).

D. Learning Motivation amidst online learning

Online learning had been the subject of various studies in the past few years. Keller and Suzuki (2004) focused their study on Learner Motivation and e-learning design. The result of their empirical studies has approved the validity of their model for the systematic design of motivationally enhanced instruction in e-learning settings with regards to diminishing dropout rate and other positive results. A study of Taran's (2005) cited in Harandi (2015) Effects of e-learning on Student's Motivation, suggests ten (10) techniques (Manding Stimuli, Anticipation, Incongruity, Concreteness, Variability, Humor, Inquiry, Participation, Break and Energizer) to catch and maintain the students' attention which is regarded as an important factor to attain motivation to learn. Furthermore, a survey conducted in the University of Colorado by Nell, A. et al (2020), they were able to identify four (4) factors that influences the learning motivation of the students in an online learning set up brought by this pandemic. This includes: (1.) Lack of structure, (2.) Change in environment, (3.) Lack of communication, (4.) Disorganization, (5.) Lack of In-person contact.

This sudden shift in our education system enables the people, especially the scholars, to compare online learning from traditional approach of learning. A study conducted by (Artino, 2008; Keller, 2008; Wighting, at al. 2008; Yukselusk and Bulut, 2007) had supported the claim that online learners were more motivated by their intrinsic motivation that their face-to-face counterpart. However, internal motivation namely: (1.) Isolated feelings, (2.) Failure in technology, (3.) Poor time management skills have been proofed as major factors that influence the learner's motivation.

E. Students' online learning experience in Philippine Context

In the Philippine context, as a third world country, the effect of Covid 19 pandemic is worst as compared to others. The entire society was been put into a strict lock down and the implementation of quarantine protocols are widely enforced. The education sector was greatly affected specially those HEI's and even both the public and private schools in all level. As a result, schools and universities in the country were forced to shut down and temporarily postponed their operations in response to the government restrictions. According to UNESCO (2020) there are approximately 28 million Filipino learners who had preferred to stay home and strictly observed the health and safety measures of the government for their own safety. But with the increasing and continuous demand of the students, the government in response had implemented policies that would aid the continuance of learning despite of several restrictions imposed by the national government. The Philippines' Commission on Higher Education (CHED), requires the majority of the HEI's to administer and adapt other flexible learning modes that would initiate learning even without having physical encounters and other alternative off-campus learning in compliance with the health and safety standards of the government (Commission on Higher Education, 2020). Some of the policies being enforced in the education system was the implementation of an online learning. The online learning approach can be administered through synchronous (real time lecture and time-based assessment) and asynchronous (delayed time activities such as a s pre- recorded video lectures and time independent assessment (Oztok et al...2013).

In LNU (Leyte Normal University), the modes of learning being practiced is the blended learning approach where learning process is done through modular means being distributed through online and is supplemented by an online/virtual consultation by the instructor done at least once a week. The submission of outputs is through online such as via Gmail or messenger and other educational mobile phone applications such as Google classroom or Google drive. It also executes asynchronous and flexible learning approach where students could learn and comply with their requirements anytime depending on their own pace.

F. Students' Motivation in Online Learning

Learning motivation is one of the factors that needs to be considered in the success of the entire learning process of the students. In fact, as an engine of learning, it influences what, how and when the students could learn Schunk & Usher, (2012). Schunk et.al., (2014) also address that students' learning success is greatly influenced or is linked to their motivation. Motivated students can perform better in class, submit all the school requirements and even excel on their own chosen career. They can even perform such complicated tasks in the class and find enjoyment and satisfaction on what they are doing Ryan and Deci (2000a, 2000b). Furthermore, Koff & Mullis (2011), argued that learning motivation drives the students to regularly attend the daily discussion and be able to effectively learn from it. It can also be reflected on the students' attendance record and class participation for every

academic related activity. However, students' motivation is categorized into two: the intrinsic (personalities) and extrinsic (learning environment) motivation. Each of them has its different impact on the students' performance and willingness to engage in learning Nayakama et al., (2014). Intrinsic motivations pertain to the act of engaging to something not because you are rewarded materially but you find enjoyment and satisfaction on it instead, while extrinsic motivations are reward driven such as incentives Santos L., (2019). However, several studies had supported those students are being more influenced by their internal driven motivation rather than by its counterpart Gustiani S. (2020). In addendum, comparable studies about online and face to face learning mode had found that online learners are (Artino, 2008; Keller, 2008; Wighting et al. 2008; Yukselturk and Bulut 2008; Keller, 2008; Wighting et al. 2008; Yukselturk and Bulut 2007).

G. Problems encountered by students during online distance learning.

Despite the conveniences of online distance learning, challenges also are encountered by students. Distance education gives students a lot more freedom in terms of how and when they interact. Sun and Rueda (2012) argue that their ability to regulate their learning becomes critical. Amadora (2020) also stated that due to the lack of interaction during online classes, students are easily distracted by smartphones, pets, deliveries, and other activities other than the ongoing online class. Because there is no face-to-face interaction, it is assumed that students will be disinterested in the online class. Tuckman (2011) discovered that students may lack opportunities to collaborate and receive feedback and social support, whereas Rost (2019) discovered that online environments can create a sense of anonymity for students, making it easier for them to withdraw or participate minimally or completely disappear from the course. These theories demonstrated that students in online learning experienced anxiety, which resulted in a lack of participation.

COVID-19 had an impact on all educational institutions around the world's physical learning methods. To continue their studies, academic institutes' higher authorities adopted online learning. Although online learning appears to be useful in protecting students' and faculty's health during the COVID-19 pandemic, some researchers have suggested that it may not be as effective as expected (Kara et al., 2020), despite the fact that it has the potential to be used with various digital tools such as tablet and smartphone (Guo et al., 2020). Online learning cannot produce good results in developing countries such as Pakistan, where the vast majority of students lack access to a good internet connection due to technical and financial constraints.

Internet connectivity is a common complaint among teachers and students, as the Philippines remains one of Asia's slowest internet countries. Wireless connectivity is another challenge, as the country has seen on television or read in the news about teachers and students climbing mountain sides or hilltops to catch wireless signals in order to use the internet (Averia, 2020). Adonis (2020) also stated that teachers suspected that the decrease in class size was due to a poor internet connection as millions of students and parents

struggled to become acquainted with the new learning platforms prompted by the new coronavirus pandemic. The Philippines' slow internet connection, posed a great challenge among students, especially those who are from remote places.

According to another study, approximately 70% of learners participated in e-learning during the lockdown period. The majority of the students used their Android phones to participate in e-learning. Students have been experiencing a variety of issues related to depression and anxiety, as well as poor internet connectivity and an unfavorable study environment at home. During this pandemic, students from remote areas and marginalized groups face enormous challenges in their studies. The unexpected shift to online learning became a measure of organizational agility with several academic institutions focusing on the transfer of educational content to the digital world rather than on online teaching and delivery methods specifically (Wu, 2020). Nonetheless, it served as a reminder of the scarcity of resources in academic institutions and the social marginalization of students, where insufficient internet access and availability, as well as a lack of cutting-edge technology, hampered organizational responsiveness and students' ability to participate in digital learning (Karademir et al., 2020).

H. Coping mechanism in dealing with learning Motivation amidst pandemic

Coping is described as the thoughts and activities utilized to deal with the internal and external demands of stressful situations (Folkman & Moskowitz 2014). In addition, Earnest and Dwyer (2010) define stress coping skills as "the ability to apply strategies that minimize and manage the stress response." Lazarus et. Al categorizes coping mechanism into two which are the problem-centered coping and emotion-centered coping. Problem-centered coping also known as direct coping aids in the active resolution of difficult situations by bringing the person into direct contact with the trigger factor and attempting to eliminate it. This type has been found to be more effective in the long run. Emotion-centered coping also known as indirect coping aids in solving difficult situations wherein the individual is more concerned and focused on what it feels and it's diminishing emotions rather than what it can do to solve the problem. In this, type of coping various strategies to minimize and postpone are involved as cited by Susanu et. Al (2020). However, Susanu et. Al (2020) claims that the two strategies cannot be claimed as better than the other one for the two of them supports each other in a way that problem-centered coping aids in finding solution and is more effective when the person is in control of the factors that triggers stress, and the emotion-centered coping has a high degree of efficiency when the trigger factor that causes stress cannot be controlled.

In contrary, Folkman and Moskowitz (2014), later on categorize that coping can be divided into four major categories: first is the problem-focused coping mechanism which focuses on the issue that is generating the distress: active coping, planning, restrained coping, and suppression of competing activities are examples of this type. Second, emotion-focused coping mechanism, with the goal of

reducing the problem's negative emotions. Positive reframing, acceptance, turning to faith, and humor are examples of this type. Third is the meaning-focused coping mechanism, in which a person employs cognitive methods to deduce and regulate the situation's meaning. Lastly, social coping mechanism (support-seeking) in which individuals engaged themselves to seek emotional or instrumental health from their community.

Furthermore, Susanu et. Al (2020) claimed that "coping, as a mechanism for prevention and adaptation to stress, runs through three stages:

- The anticipation or warning is the stage in which the subject prepares for confrontation and evaluates its strategies and cost;
- The impact or confrontation is the person's response to the stressful stimulus;
- Post-confrontation is the analysis of the significance of what happened."

Every individual coping strategy is effective in all situation because the effectiveness of a specific coping strategy depends on its suitability to the factors that triggers the stress or stressors (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984). According Ntoumanis et al (2009) by controlling the evaluation or experience of stress, motivation influences coping techniques.

The connection between coping strategies and academic performance has been established. Khan (2013) discovered that the relationship between coping strategies or coping mechanism and academic performance was not strong. On the contrary, Kadiravan & Kumar (2012) revealed that coping strategies has a positive impact to students when it comes to enhancing their academic performance. Similarly, Sullivan (2010) found out that coping strategies can helped the students to perform in their academic through the aid of various coping strategies.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

With the title "Exploring the Factors Affecting Learning Motivation of LNU Social Studies Major Amidst Online Learning Experience", the researchers employed qualitative study approach for this study in order to obtain an in-depth understanding of factors and experiences affecting students' learning motivation amidst online learning experience. Qualitative research is a method of inquiry that explores a social or human situation and is based on several methodological traditions of inquiry. It focuses on the "why" instead of just the "what" in order to understand the social phenomenon through everyday human experiences (Cresswell, 2014). Instead of using statistical and logical procedures, the researchers will be using the Phenomenological research approach as it will allow the researcher to reflect on the lived experiences of Social Studies major amidst online learning. A phenomenological study, according to Creswell (2007), "describes the meaning for multiple persons of their lived experiences of a concept or a phenomenon". To do this, a researcher will usually choose a phenomenon to study. Furthermore, the researches will

particularly use the hermeneutic phenomenology which is an interpretative process in which the researchers will make an interpretation, of the meaning of the lived experiences. This technique was used to acquire a better grasp of an individual's experience and to provide a general summary of all participant experiences (van Manen, 1997). This design, in particular, allows for the collection of data from each participant while also capturing the fundamental experience of all participants. The hermeneutic approach to phenomenology presupposes those participants have encountered the phenomenon under study, that they regard these experiences as conscious (Van Manen, 1997), and that the growth of descriptions, not explanations or analyses, is at the heart of these experiences (Moustakas, 1994).

B. Research Locale

This study will be conducted in Leyte Normal University. Leyte Normal University is a non-profit public higher-education institution, established in 1921, and is located in the suburban setting of the small city of Tacloban City, Eastern Visayas. And it is officially recognized by the Commission on Higher Education of the Philippines, Leyte Normal University (LNU) is a small coeducational Philippine higher education institution, with enrollment range of 5,000-5,999 students. Leyte Normal University (LNU) offers courses and programs leading to officially recognized higher education degrees such as bachelor degrees, master degrees, doctorate degrees in several areas of study and is, specifically located in Paterno St., Downtown Tacloban, City. This 100 years old Philippine higher-education institution has a selective admission policy based on entrance examinations. LNU also provides several academic and non-academic facilities and services to students including a library, sports facilities, study abroad and exchange programs, as well as administrative services.

The Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in Social Studies students in Leyte Normal University has a total of 309 students' which are currently occupying 15-35 students in each section.

C. Participants of the Study

The participants of this study included the BSED-Social Studies students at Leyte Normal University. The Social Studies students were selected as participants of this study to determine the factors affecting the learning motivation of Social Studies majors in LNU amidst their online learning experience. The researchers find the participants to be reliable sources since they are one of the million students who experience the difficulty of learning amidst the COVID-19 pandemic due to the lack of motivation they can see and experience within themselves and the environment that surrounds them. The study is limited only to the fourteen identified students who are currently studying via online learning set-up at Leyte Normal University, particularly located in Tacloban City. All the identified participants are students under the Bachelor of Secondary Education Major in Social Studies for the School Year 2021–2022.

The researchers will utilize purposive sampling method for this study, in which they will select members of the population to take part in this study based on their own

assessment. According to Dudovskiy (2011), purposive sampling is a non-probability sampling technique in which elements chosen for the sample are selected based on the researcher's judgment. Researchers typically claim that by applying sound judgment, they can produce a representative sample and save time and money. Moreover, since this study is qualitative in design which primarily aims to obtain in-depth understanding of a lived experiences and current situation of the students, nonprobability sampling methods such as the purposive sampling techniques is an appropriate method to be used in order to identify a sample, based on some considerations of the researchers, who would participate in the study. By using this method, the researchers would assure to address the biases in the selection of the participants considering that all social studies students in Leyte Normal University, even those who are top performing, are facing motivational crisis within themselves specially amidst online learning experiences.

D. Data Collection Method

In compliance with the health and safety protocols set forth by the national government, the entire data collection will be conducted virtually at home specifically via virtual interview. As a preliminary step, the researchers sought the approval and permission of the school president, Dr. Evelyn B. Aguirre and Mr. Ryan G. Destura, Social studies head for the overall conduct of the study. The researchers applied hermeneutics phenomenology as an approach in the collection of the data. It is an approach which is based on the analysis of the most complex aspects of human life, of what is beyond the quantifiable aspects. As what do Husserl (1998) argues on his study, he explains it as a paradigm that tries to explain the nature of the things, the essence and the veracity of the phenomena with the initial aim on understanding the complexity of the lived experiences. Qualitative research is a method of inquiry that explores a social or human situation and is based on several methodological traditions of inquiry were undertaken to obtain the essential data needed for the study: In the qualitative research, using hermeneutics phenomenology the researchers will interview the respondents through the use of an unstructured, usually open-ended questionnaire to elicit the participants' views and beliefs (Creswell, 2014). The respondents will describe their personal experiences through conversational in-depth interview. After the interview, the themes are created based on what they had discussed and the resulting perception of the individual's establish a holistic picture of the participant. Finally, the data will be analyzed through the use of Thematic Content Diagram.

E. Ethical Consideration

In the pursuit of this study, some ethical considerations were ensured by the researchers in order to secure the reliability and validity of the study. First, prior to the conduct of the interview the participants were given the full consent on their participation and were given the right to decide whether to withdraw at any stage if they wish to do. In a nutshell, the students' participation is purely voluntary and is based on an informed consent. They were also assured for their privacy and the confidentiality of the research data based from the information that they will give to the researchers in adherence to the Data Privacy Act of 2012.

The use of offensive, discriminatory and unnecessary language in the formulation of the questionnaires and interviews were strictly condemned. Proper acknowledgement and citations of the works of other authors used in any part of the paper were also prioritized. Lastly, all the data collected in the study were objectively discussed and analyzed to arrive at a valid and fair results.

F. Research Reflexivity

In these times of pandemic, where flexible learning has been introduced, each of us, instructors, students, and academic staff, has been profoundly impacted, particularly students. As researchers, the aim is to provide insights that require the majority of HEIs to administer and adapt other flexible learning modes that would initiate learning even without physical encounters, as well as other alternative off-campus learning in accordance with government health and safety standards. The researchers expect that by conducting this study, participants will be able to express their thoughts, feelings and experiences about the implementation of flexible online learning. It's also worth noting that the researchers are students who have dealt with similar issues in a crisis community and are fluent in CHED, which could influence how the data are handled. To avoid being partial and biased, the researchers double-checked data sources, looked for alternate interpretations, discussed findings with colleagues, and double-checked members. Interviews were also transcribed verbatim and submitted back to the subject for accuracy and cross-checking when analyzing the data.

G. Data Analysis

The researchers have chosen the thematic analytic approach as it is a flexible yet detailed analytic technique. Analysis is essentially realistic and semantic in nature when attempting to determine the lived experiences, thoughts, or behaviors throughout a data set. Hence, thematic analysis is an appropriate way of analysis (Kiger & Varpio, 2020). This method was adopted in order to identify the participants' consciously held experiences and how these experiences intentionally shaped their behaviors. Themes were identified and organized using a theoretical framework, which meant that coding was done with specific problems in mind. The researchers identified major themes after reading through the text and taking initial notes, and generally looking through the data to get familiar with it. Following the creation of the essential themes, the transcript and coded elements were evaluated to ensure the authenticity of the themes that were created.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The researchers employed hermeneutic phenomenological research design, a qualitative research method which deals more on the lived experiences of students in the BSED Social Studies major at Leyte Normal University, who have identified factors that affect their learning motivation. The meaning of their experiences emerged after their narratives were transcribed. Developed core ideas were presented in the preceding sections along with their corresponding major themes. The fourteen purposively selected participants of the study were given

enough time to answer the question that the researchers had asked them.

Factors that affect the learning Motivation of the Social Studies Students amidst the online learning experience.

The factors that affects the learning Motivation of the Social Studies Students amidst the online learning experience are encapsulated into essential themes and thematic statements as shown in Table 1.

Essential Themes	Thematic Statements
Poor internet connection	<p>These could be poor internet connectivity, lot of works/assignments to submit on, and not getting timely feedbacks about my studies. ...and I have a hard time with my internet connection. ...and slow internet connection. Internet connection problem because I lived in Jaro, Leyte an in that area the internet connection is very slow and when there is an online class, sometimes I got disconnected. The factors that affect my motivation to learn, like internet connection, sometimes there's no internet connection and power interruption especially at times when there are online classes and recitation I really feel demotivated. These could be poor internet connectivity, lot of works/assignments to submit on, and not getting timely feedbacks about my studies. Poor internet connection and signal.</p>
Poor Peer Relationship	<p>I feel that it is difficult especially that the interaction with my classmates is limited. Also, the type of interaction we had unlike in a face to face set up, online learning hinders you to be with someone whom you can trust more. Virtual relationship is not that reliable as compared to a personal relationship. I can't understand our lessons, I'm having a hard time communicating to my classmates and teachers.</p>
Non-conductive learning set-up	<p>Noises from my background and time management. Noises from the background makes me lose my interest. There is no interaction that we feel unlike the traditional one. I find very distracting doing such as household chores, background noise from neighbors. In the morning there are background noises so in that case I adjust and I need to do in early morning. I feel disadvantaged because interaction is not significant in an online learning mode. I really felt that the implementation of online learning class set up is antipoor and very insensitive actions knowing that not all students have the capacity. I feel uncomfortable with this online set up. Learning is limited, given that the professors only give us modules which is some part of it are not being discussed and the set deadlines for the activities are not enough to accomplish the module.</p>
Family Issues and Instability	<p>I have experience financial problem especially we are two studying in college and my brother attending limited face-to-face classes. Lack of support (moral support) from my parents, teachers and friends. Responsibility as a student and as an elder sister always have a conflict. There are times that we don't have food and no load because of this kind of situation. I can say that financial matter is one of the factors that greatly affects my motivation to learn. As a working student, it makes me more difficult to focus on my study. Sometimes, I cannot comply some of my requirements on time.</p>
Lack of Resources	<p>I don't have access from various gadgets, I only have single smartphone and it hard to attend classes like to sharing screen of your reporting and recording the ongoing class. Resources such as laptop, unstable load support and computer.</p>
Health Related Factors	<p>Pressure, a lot of things to do, i can't understand our lessons, the new set-up of learning, and stress. I feel stressed and drained. It was so stressful to me because I am eager to learn but this situation give me reason not to. I feel lonely, and I find learning not fun anymore. I feel disappointed in myself and sad at the same time perhaps I cannot move my body and mind to neither accomplish my tasks and attend online classes I feel pressure because I have lot of things to do and it made me feel stress. I felt sad and somehow afraid because face to face classes is much more productive than online learning.</p>

	<p>I was anxious about it because it will be the first time for me to be into online learning and, I was used to the traditional set-up.</p> <p>Anxiety and stress for always thinking about modules.</p> <p>I felt pressured and challenged as I don't have the capacity to support my studies in this type of learning modality.</p> <p>Online learning gave me the feeling of always being anxious due to the pressure of the deadlines, and the fear that I may not meet the expectations of the teacher, especially when I was in first year, I had a hard time attending online classes because there are concepts from the lesson that I cannot understand and self- learning sometimes is not effective.</p> <p>It affects my mental and physical health. For the last few weeks, I notice that I can't answer my modules anymore and I can't learn the lessons but, in my mind, I force myself to believe that I need to pass my activities even if it's not well-made</p>
Teacher's Behavior and Personality	<p>There are professors/ instructors that doesn't know how to understand the situation of other students. They tend to become inconsiderate sometimes. There are also some toxic classmates that would poison you and make you feel offended. It makes me lose my confident to actively participate in the class and destructs my motivation to learn.</p>

Table 1: Factors Affecting Learning Motivation

A. Poor Internet Connection

Internet connectivity is a common complaint among students. They have been continuously experiencing poor internet connection during online learning because their location has a weak signal. This factor has led students to feel demotivated from online learning because they are frequently disconnected from their online classes due to poor internet connectivity in their area. This concern often happens as the Philippines remains one of Asia's slowest internet countries. Wireless connectivity is another challenge, as the country has seen on television or read in the news about teachers and students climbing mountain sides or hilltops to catch wireless signals in order to use the internet (Averia, 2020). Adonis (2020) also stated that teachers suspected that the decrease in class size was due to a poor internet connection as millions of students and parents struggled to become acquainted with the new learning platforms prompted by the new coronavirus pandemic. The Philippines' slow internet connection posed a great challenge among students, especially those who are from remote places. Nonetheless, it served as a reminder of the scarcity of resources in academic institutions and the social marginalization of students, where insufficient internet access and availability, as well as a lack of cutting-edge technology, hampered organizational responsiveness and students' ability to participate in digital learning (Karademir et al., 2020). Although online learning appears to be useful in protecting students' and faculty's health during the COVID-19 pandemic, some researchers have suggested that it may not be as effective as expected (Kara et al., 2020), despite the fact that it has the potential to be used with various digital tools such as tablets and smartphones (Guo et al., 2020). Online learning cannot produce good results in developing countries such as Pakistan, where the vast majority of students lack access to a good internet connection due to technical and financial constraints.

B. Poor Peer Relationship

Schools aren't just places where students learn new things from books; they're also places where friendships emerge and happy memories are made. However, since the COVID pandemic, there has been a poor peer relationship among the students. This includes lack of social interaction,

social isolation, lack of moral support from their parents, teachers, and friends. This has a significant impact on a student's mental health. In an online learning environment, students who do not have regular academic social interaction experience more learning difficulties. This association is in line with previous studies, which imply that distance education gives students a lot more freedom in terms of how and when they interact. Sun and Rueda (2012) argue that their ability to regulate their learning becomes critical. Amadora (2020) also stated that due to the lack of interaction during online classes, students are easily distracted by smartphones, pets, deliveries, and other activities other than the ongoing online class. Because there is no face-to-face interaction, it is assumed that students will be disinterested in the online class. In online learning, the lack of social interaction leads to feelings of loneliness, lack of motivation, and isolation. Moreover, in the Achievement Motivation Theory of McLelland, human motives are related to the achievement motive, affiliation motive, the sexual motive, and the power motive. McLelland postulates that people become more motivated if these needs are met. It is stated in McLelland's theory that there is a need for affiliation, which means establishing and maintaining a positive affective relationship with another person. This relationship is most adequately described by the word "friendship." And also, in Maslow's hierarchy of needs, he also postulated the love and belongingness needs, which include friendship and family relationships, and in order to achieve this need, physical and emotional intimacy and emotional bonding are necessary to achieve this need. Therefore, if this need for affiliation, love, and belongingness is not met and acquired, students will feel demotivated in learning.

C. Non-conductive learning set-up

This happens when the curriculum does not support or undermine students' well-being, depending on the extent to which it fosters students' autonomous motivation. In which students are subjected to learning disruptions, such as loud background noises, which interfere with their ability to concentrate in class. Due to such disruptions, students are disinclined to attend classes. As a result, students experience minimal classroom engagement, in which individuals who exhibit a need for affiliation seek

interactions with other people (Moore & Rotter, 2010). As a result, it influences students' cognitive development, making the online learning environment unpleasant for unmotivated students.

D. Family Issues and Instability

One of the identified factors that affect students' motivation amidst online learning set-up is family issues and instability, including financial problems, lack of moral support, and poor family relationships. These are the things that cause them to feel demotivated. It was mentioned by one of the respondents that financial security is the one that makes them feel demotivated considering that there are two or more siblings in the family who need financial support for their studies as well. In Maslow's hierarchy of needs, security or safety needs are one thing that guarantees people will be motivated. At this level of need, it encompasses financial security and stability to sustain their daily needs in life. In addition, the respondents also identified the lack of moral support and poor family relationships as factors that dictate their motivation to learn. The absence of moral support from their parents and the feeling of loneliness makes them demotivated to study and learn. In Maslow's hierarchy of needs, the need for love and belongingness also contributes to the behavior (motivation) of the students towards accomplishing a certain goal. McClellan's Achievement Motivation Theory also suggests that people are motivated to varying degrees depending on their needs for achievement, need for affiliation, and need for power. The need for affiliation pertains to the need of the students to become part of a family or a group and build intimate relationships with their family or other people.

E. Lack of Resources

The lack of resources such as gadgets like laptop, mobile phones, computer, and access to an internet connection also causes students to face difficulty in complying with all of their course requirements and actively engaging and participating in online classes. The respondents assert that not having the financial capacity to buy mobile data or access to reliable and stringent internet connection makes them feel inferior and, worst of all, demotivated. They also claim that the unavailability of gadgets, which are undeniably helpful in an online learning set-up, also contributes to their lack of motivation to learn. Furthermore, the Philippines' slow internet connection posed a great challenge among students, especially those who are from remote places. Nonetheless, it served as a reminder of the scarcity of resources in academic institutions and the social marginalization of students, where insufficient internet access and availability, as well as a lack of cutting-edge technology, hampered organizational responsiveness and students' ability to participate in digital learning (Karademir et al., 2020).

F. Health Related Factors

One of the factors that affect students learning motivation is their mental and physical health. Students feel disinterested and demotivated to join online classes because they feel anxious, stress, drained, exhausted, and pressured with their modules and deadlines. This result is aligned with the previous study, states that online learning poses a threat to the learners' physical and psychological wellbeing as they would spend more time staring at their computer screens, which could emit harmful radiation that could directly damage their eyes (Gustiani, 2020). Moreover, some students also complain that online learning makes them feel less eager to learn because most of the time they feel stressed and lonely, and as a result, they find learning not fun and interesting just like before. Students also feel drained and exhausted because of a lack of enough rest in the middle of compiled activities to be accomplished in just a short period of time (Simamora, 2020). Online learning also has a great impact on the psychological and mental well-being of students. This is basically due to some circumstances that are far beyond one's control, such as poor internet connectivity and financial problems that have a direct impact on the students' performance and quarterly remarks. Online learning is a very challenging and demanding approach to learning. Others who are vulnerable are even prone to experiencing depression (Simamora, 2020).

G. Teachers Behavior and Personality

Teachers' behaviour towards students is undeniably an important factor that needs to be considered in determining the motivation of the students to learn a specific subject area. Based on the survey conducted, students identified that teachers' behaviour and personality also influenced their will and interest in learning. Some of them argue that there are some professors who don't know how to recognize the student's efforts and struggles just to overcome all the struggles in this new mode of learning. In Maslow's theory, he emphasizes the psychological needs of humans, which he called belongingness and the need for love, wherein he relates them to human connection. On the other hand, McClelland's theory calls it a need for affiliation, which he also defines as having an affective connection with other people. Students' struggles to establish connections with the teachers, difficulty in communicating, such as not getting timely feedback from the teachers, and teachers' being inconsiderate affected the student-teacher relationship negatively, causing the students to be unmotivated.

H. How do these factors affected the learning Motivation of the Social Studies students

The participants of the study shared their experiences of how these factors that they had identified affected their learning motivation.

Theme	Statement
Distracted	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In the morning there are background noises so in that case I adjust and I need to do in early morning • Noises from the background makes me lose my interest because I lose my focus every time there will be classes, • As a working student, it makes me more difficult to focus on my study.
Inefficiency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • time management affects my motivation to learn because as a student and as an elder sister always have a conflict. • I find it difficult to balance my studies and responsibilities at our house. • I cannot comply some of my requirements on time because time management is really a difficult task to
Unproductive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It made me feel less productive. • I don't have energy anymore, I'm always tired in studying, and I'm not really motivated • It made me less productive and to procrastinate more
Demotivated	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Noises from the background makes me lose my interest because I lose my focus every time there will be classes, • It gives me hard time; it makes me feel unmotivated to learn and struggle attending classes • feel lonely, and I find learning not fun anymore • It decreases my motivation and enthusiasm to pursue my studies • it tends to make me feel disappointed in myself and feel sad at the same time

Table 2: How do these factors Affect Learning Motivation

I. Distracted

Distraction is one of the issues that students are facing amidst online learning, as they get easily distracted during online classes and tend to lose their focus. On the word of the participant, "I find it very distracting because of doing household chores and background noise from neighbors." Others claim that they get distracted by other social media applications such as YouTube, TikTok, Facebook, and other social media applications. Moreover, in the study of Amadora (2020), it was stated that due to the lack of interaction during online classes, students are easily distracted by smartphones, pets, deliveries, and other activities other than the ongoing online class. Because there is no face-to-face interaction, it is assumed that students will be disinterested in the online class. This problem occurs due to the lack of interaction during online classes, which is associated with Maslow's Theory of Human Motivation, related to belongingness and love needs that emphasize connection and relationship with people, and McClellan's theory of motivation, related to the need for affiliation.

J. Inefficiency

Inefficiency is the state of not achieving maximum productivity; a failure to make the best use of time or resources. Students during online learning become inefficient in complying with their requirements because they are experiencing difficulties in balancing their time. Students during online learning become inefficient in complying with their requirements because they are experiencing difficulties in balancing their time. Artino, 2008, et al., clearly said that poor time management skills have been proven as a major factor that influences the learner's motivation. Furthermore, a study conducted by Harnet, (2016) cited by Gustiani, S. (2020), found that the

absence of both intrinsic and extrinsic motivations in every student is referred to as amotivation. It occurs when students feel unwillingness and low driving force in learning, self-degradation, and low self-efficacy. They believe that learning outcomes are irrelevant as they don't satisfy their expectations and have less value in returns. Sison et al. (2021) claim that "Motivation and self-efficacy influence each other, and having such good self-efficacy can motivate the students to do well in school and increase their academic success".

K. Unproductive

Motivation is also referred to as the engine of learning (Paris & Turner, 1994). It serves as the driving force of an individual to actively engage and accomplish certain tasks. Ryan and Deci (2000a, 2000b) suggested that motivated learners are capable of engaging in demanding learning activities that engage them actively in discovering appropriate techniques to support their learning, enjoy them, and demonstrate competence, persistence, and creative learning in their studies. On the other hand, due to low motivation level, students tend to become unproductive on their study. Respondents on the said interview testified, that the low learning motivation brought by this online learning set up made them feel less productive and tolerated them to procrastinate more. There are times that they become less energetic and feels exhausted causing them to loss their motivation to learn. McClellan's achievement motivation theory, Daft (2008) stated the need for Achievement is "the desire to accomplish something difficult, attain a high standard of success, master complex tasks, and surpass others" (p. 233). Individuals who exhibit the need for Achievement seek to accomplish realistic but challenging goals (Moore & Rotter, 2010).

L. Demotivated

Of all the challenges facing students right now, a lack of motivation in online learning mode is one of the most frustrating. This lack of motivation derives directly from the numerous other obstacles that students encounter, such as lack of engagement with classmates, difficulty studying in a virtual format, distracting home surroundings, lack of access to proper study areas, and so on. Demotivation does not imply that a positive incentive driving a particular conduct has been ignored; rather, it implies that the resulting force has been weakened by powerful negating influences. Furthermore, finding means to examine variables (e.g., internal or external) of demotivation as they are astutely seen by particular learners is critically crucial. They are actively engaged in learning at the same time, which may lead to demotivation. Motivation of the students rely on the intrinsic and extrinsic. To study and to be able to learn what makes student motivated and demotivated, we can study the two variables of motivation which is the intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. This is based on the theoretical foundations of McClelland's Achievement Motivation Theory and Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs Theory of Motivation. The framework's notion demonstrates the link between two theories that would support the two variables, intrinsic and extrinsic motivation

factors, which have been frequently utilized to investigate students' reasons for online involvement (e.g., Mortens, Gulikers, & Bastiaens, 2004; Xie et al., 2006). Extrinsic influences and variables influence student learning motivation through external rewards such as grading systems, employee evaluations, awards and accolades, and other people's respect and admiration., factors, and some extrinsic motivation that affects student learning. Intrinsic motivation is distinct from other types of motivation and is based on an individual's personality. Intrinsic motivation encompasses a wide range of notions, including our underlying values, interests, and personal morals. These factors may vary as the student's motivation to learn grows.

Coping mechanisms or personal remedies of the students in dealing with the Factors that affects their learning Motivation.

In spite of the factors that affected the learning motivation of the students, they were able to stand and continue their studies because they believed in themselves that they could cope and succeed in life despite those trials and difficulties. Presented in Table 3 are the coping mechanisms of the students.

Essential Themes	Thematic Statements
Peer-Support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I do podcast to find word that will make me feel motivated to do more and to continue and be aware of what is happening. (2) • I sometimes watch funny movies, motivational advices (4) • ...talking to my classmates through chats and social media so that it can motivate me (5) • ...talking with my mama (7) • I also spend time in finding circle of friends that will encourage me to feel motivated and whom I could trust the most.
Time Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I also do manage my time wisely (6) • I finish all the house chores to make sure I am able to attend classes without any disturb. (9) • Time management (10) • I set time to do my tasks (12) • I made a checklist of my modules; I do time management (14)
Rest	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I do make sure that I am getting enough rest, and take breaks when I am mentally and physically exhausted. (6) • Sleeping (7) • I'm giving myself a time to rest and enjoy, I'm prioritizing my health while I'm learning, (10) • have a little break every after I finished answering mymodule, I also do meditation or self-reflection to sort things out (14)
Perseverance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ...directing myself to my ultimate goal, to succeed in life. • I focused more on the things that would help me in my journey and the things that I value most. • I want to get my old self back that is eager to learn, eager to achieve things, face my fear, and finish my studies.

Table 3: Coping Mechanism

M. Time Management

Time management is defined as the process of carefully managing and organizing your time either for work or for school to maximize the efforts in order to effectively and efficiently accomplish specific task. It is too difficult to attend to your online class while doing some household chores at the same time. That's why we have time

management to organize the things that you want to accomplish. Sullivan (2010) found out that coping strategies can helped the students to perform in their academic through the aid of various coping strategies. Time management is one of the identified coping mechanisms of the respondents. Students are able to cope up with their struggles on learning motivation through effective time

management. This is done by having a check list of the tasks to be accomplished in every given period. They find ways as well to balance their time for studying and for attending some household chores respectively. This is for them to not be overwhelmed on the pile of works given by their teachers.

N. Peer-support system

Students whose motivation was affected by online learning were able to cope with the support of their friends, classmates, parents, influencers, and podcasters who gave motivational advice. Folkman and Moskowitz (2014) clearly stated in their final major category of coping mechanism the social coping mechanism (support-seeking), in which individuals engage in seeking emotional or instrumental health from their community. Furthermore, psychological needs such as belongingness and love are included in Maslow's hierarchy of needs theory of motivation. Social needs, or needs for belonging (accepted by others) and giving and receiving friendship and love, are at Maslow's third level. People can meet these needs through informal social groups on and off the job. Students will be motivated to learn if this need is addressed. The further up in the hierarchy a student is, the more motivated he or she is, and hence the learner will learn more effectively. Maslow's hierarchy is a framework for understanding how pupils are driven to learn. Students cannot progress to the next level until the lowest tier of the hierarchy is met.

O. Taking a rest as coping mechanism

During online learning, students are expected to sit for more than an hour in front of their computers, laptops, and cellphones to attend their online classes. Students are exhausted because of answering their modules online, late-night studying, and cram sessions, and this has led students to experience health problems such as insomnia, anxiety, mental strain, and fatigue. However, these students reward themselves with enough rest as their coping mechanism. In line with the previous study, stress coping abilities are also defined by Earnest and Dwyer (2010) as "the ability to employ techniques that decrease and moderate the stress reaction." Taking a break from the online learning method restores attention and relieves mental strain and fatigue. Many studies have discovered that taking a few moments to relax and refresh is critical to gaining productivity, achievement, and a good attitude in the future. This is especially true for learners who sit in front of a computer for long periods of time. Taking a rest is a problem-centered coping mechanism. According to Lazarus et al., problem-centered coping, also known as direct coping, aids in the active resolution of difficult situations by bringing the person into direct contact with the trigger factor and attempting to eliminate it. This type has been found to be more effective in the long run. Because the effectiveness of a certain coping strategy depends on its compatibility with the circumstances that create the stress or stressors, no single coping strategy is effective in all situations (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984). According to Ntoumanis et al. (2009), motivation influences coping mechanisms by affecting the evaluation or experience of stress, and according to Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs, it is the freedom of a person

to seek security and safety. protecting their safety against emotional instability and health. If a person does not feel safe in an environment, they will seek to find safety before they attempt to meet any higher-level needs.

P. Perseverance

Due to COVID-19 constraints, students are persevering through a hard semester that comprises primarily of online study. As students age, online learning also helps them develop tenacity by empowering them to become independent learners. Perseverance stories (stories about students who overcame obstacles in school) come in different shapes and sizes. Academic perseverance is defined as a student's ability to continue participating in academic activities despite difficulties or barriers. Perseverance drives students to achieve and accomplish something. The need for achievement theory aims to explain why some people are more motivated to succeed than others. It is founded on two psychological principles: an individual's desire to succeed and his or her desire to avoid failure. The individual may fail to achieve this goal, but the concern over competition with a standard of excellence still enables one to identify the goal sought as an achievement goal. This, then, is our generic definition of "Achievement" (p. 181) by McClelland et al. (1958). Individuals with perseverance have the potential to achieve things that will lead to their self-actualization. The term "self-actualization" refers to reaching your maximum potential as a human. Self-actualization needs, also known as self-fulfillment needs, are at the top of Maslow's pyramid.

V. SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents a summary of the findings, conclusions based on the data analysis, and recommendations.

A. Summary

The findings of the study were summarized according to the statement of the problems stated in Chapter I.

- Factors that affect the learning Motivation of the Social Studies Students amidst the online learning experience include:
 - Poor Internet Connection
 - Poor Peer Relationships
 - Family Issues and Instability
 - Non-Conducive Learning Set-Up
 - Lack Of Resources
 - Health-Related Factors
 - Teacher's Personality and Behavior
- How does the factors affects the learning Motivation of the Social Studies students include:
 - Distracted
 - Unproductive
 - Inefficient
 - Demotivated

• The coping mechanisms or personal remedies of the students in dealing with the Factors that affects their learning Motivation include:

- peer support
- time management
- taking enough rest
- perseverance

B. Conclusions

Learning motivation is the student's driving force to actively participate and engage in the daily learning process. It dictates the behavior of the students towards achieving certain tasks and acts as an impetus to achieving higher goals in life. Without learning motivation, a student could find it difficult to establish the real essence and purpose of going to school every day. Thus, low or absence of learning motivation is a considerable issue that students are struggling with in our current education system. It should not just be ignored by the government because the lack of learning motivation could not just affect the welfare of the child but the future of his family and the community. The researchers were able to identify several factors that influence the learning motivation of BSED social studies students at LNU through this study. This includes poor internet connection, poor peer relationships, family issues and instability, non-conducive learning set-up, lack of resources, health-related factors, and the teacher's personality and behavior. However, the study also revealed the impact of these factors on the learning motivation of the students. It includes being distracted, unproductive, inefficient, and not feeling motivated. Moreover, the students' coping mechanisms for this problem encompass seeking for peer support, effective time management, taking enough rest, and perseverance.

C. Recommendations

Based on the conclusion, the following recommendations were drawn;

For the administrators, we recommend this study to further improve the curriculum in identifying strategies that will motivate students to cope with the demands of an online learning platform.

For teachers, we recommend this study to guide teachers in motivating their students who are struggling in their studies in the online learning platform, as well as to improve their learning materials and teaching styles in today's context.

For parents and guardians, we recommend this study to help and motivate their children in the online learning set-up. They can also give them their full support in their quest for an online learning platform.

For the students, we recommend this study to use their intrinsic and extrinsic motivation in their studies, as well as their online learning coping mechanisms to better their way of learning in the new mode of education.

For future researchers, this research study on the factors that affect learning motivation during an online learning experience can be replicated by using other

variables in order to expand on the study's findings, making it an ongoing process. The students' coping mechanisms included many strategies for dealing with the learning motivation, such as peer support, time management, getting enough rest, and perseverance. However, there is a need to investigate others in the future, such as achievement motivation, which was mentioned in one of the articles, and possibly work on developing the strategies that are already in place. As a result, the research used in the study varies depending on the school, course, year, and students.

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